

USING VARIOUS TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE

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Annotation: *The purpose of this study is to learn more about the methods and resources the English teacher in Uzbekistan employed to teach speaking to seventh-grade students. A case study research design was used here. The observation logs, interview questions, and documentation are the study's tools. The researcher monitors every step of the seventh-grade class's English teaching procedure. For extra information, the researcher also spoke with five pupils and five teachers in interviews. Data from observations are confirmed using the documentation. The study's findings demonstrate that English teachers employ a variety of instructional strategies, including question-answer display, translation, drilling, and discussion.*

Keywords: *boost linguistic ability, learning process, media literacy, data, teaching English, literature, development, techniques.*

Utilizing information technology and contemporary teaching techniques facilitates speedy assimilation of new information. A teacher can complete a certain curriculum by fusing various methodologies. In this way, both educators and learners gained knowledge of cutting-edge techniques for teaching foreign languages. You will then be able to select the strategy that will help you attain your objectives. It can be beneficial to employ a range of teaching and learning techniques. Little-by-little instruction builds on the student's pre-existing knowledge base. The emphasis is initially placed on pronunciation. The first prerequisite of a natural speaker, in Harmer's opinion, is pronunciation. The instructor should focus on pronunciation at the beginning of the training procedure.

Although grammar and vocabulary are important, it's useless if the speaker mispronounces them. Native speakers also can understand speech with grammatical errors if the speaker pronounces the words correctly. Therefore, in teaching, the most focus is on pronunciation. In this

case, the utilization of various audios of native speakers gives good results. The teacher should teach the right pronunciation of letters and words during the lesson.

Because of the knowledge that children initially acquire in school, there are more people in our community who are interested in learning a language today. The updating and adaptation of teaching methods to meet the demands of the contemporary knowledge-based society is one of the teacher's most crucial jobs. This entails not only taking ownership of the educational process but also having the capacity to evaluate its performance and make improvements. The ability of the teacher to adapt to various circumstances and address the unique requirements of each student is equally crucial.

In addition to having a theoretical understanding of the competencies and being aware of the skills and abilities needed for vocational training, teachers should also be able to implement and use these competencies in daily classroom activities. If you need to show off a skill. Additionally, it is crucial to address the problem of inspiring teachers to develop their abilities.

The teachers of English also employ a variety of instructional tools, including oral, written, visual, and multimodal. However, the majority of English teachers employ printed materials and question-answer displays as their primary teaching strategies. The majority of pupils are curious about the educational methods and instructional materials that the teacher uses when instructing speaking. The researcher has numerous recommendations for the English teacher based on the findings. It would be preferable if the English teacher could offer additional teaching strategies and resources. Additionally, it might present different perspectives from English teachers on instructional methods and media. For future researchers looking into a related topic, the researcher advises that they focus their research on a more specialized area, such as teaching methods or teaching media. By doing so, the topic can be examined in greater detail. Newspapers were the first form of communication to adopt the term "media" more than 200 years ago. Today's media can mean many different things. There are mass media, print media, visual media, and social media, for instance.

Media can be a part of active learning techniques like case studies or group discussions. A film clip, a song you hear on the radio, a podcast of a lecture, or an article from the newspaper all qualify as media. Students have the option of producing original material. Student video projects, for

instance, can be a potent learning tool. Traditional learning methods are complemented by the use of media to improve teaching and learning. Bridges are built between students' prior knowledge and the course's learning objectives through effective instruction. Using media in the classroom engages students, helps them retain knowledge, spurs enthusiasm in the subject, and shows how many ideas are relevant.

Like all other teaching methods, media should be used sparingly during the educational process. Media can be used to anchor ideas or encourage conversation. However, before integrating media or asking their students to utilize or create media in their courses, teachers must take a number of crucial factors into account. This section discusses how to use media successfully, lists some typical errors to avoid, and explains how to get students involved in making their own media. Students can be prepared in these essential learning areas through data-driven teaching. Additionally, research is increasingly supporting the notion that active engagement pedagogies improve retention and encourage transfer by boosting both student learning recall and persistence in an area of study. As a result, teaching with data can foster both the broad learning qualities admired by employers as well as a deeper and more enduring comprehension of the subject material. Direct instruction, active learning instructional methods, and student projects can all make use of media.

To generate interest in and advance knowledge of the content being taught, lecturers might make use of the available media resources. This traditional method is teacher-centric and pushes material upon the student. Through the use of media, the instructor can help inexperienced students transmit their knowledge from experts. Choosing the best media channel to reach their students is a constant issue for teachers due to the rapid pace of technological change. Additionally, educators can produce their own content to effectively and efficiently impart knowledge. The usage of already-available media resources can also be used to involve students and support active learning techniques that encourage deeper learning. For instance, using examples in the classroom, working in groups to solve problems, and offering more engaging lecture presentations are all made possible by media.

Student-produced content can be used in place of or in addition to typical undergraduate research. Students can be encouraged to reflect on themselves and communicate by having them complete a digital storytelling project. We are frequently accustomed to the conjugation techniques when instructing elementary school kids. And maybe most

crucially, it's important to engage kids in the learning processes. For instance, several films and games at the beginner or elementary level must be employed. Children become more interested in the language as a result, and it also helps to focus their attention more on the lesson. Additionally, students who are properly motivated will be more interested in and motivated to study the English language. The rationale is that by providing such an incentive, children's psychology is encouraged to show a greater interest in language learning. Through the use of such cutting-edge techniques, language teaching can produce successful results.

Through specific learning strategies, such as one that can boost students' enthusiasm, a skilled English teacher in primary school prepares the kids to the best of their ability, especially in the study of the English language. Using the appropriate English language teaching methodologies and achieving the learning objectives in accordance with the characteristics of the students will support the teaching and learning process. Modern education presents difficulties in finding teaching methods that foster meaningful learning and inspire young students to take an interest in learning. Therefore, it may be claimed that a key factor in determining how well a teaching approach works is if it exists.

Our use of information technology tools will benefit from this. The student's speech will then develop and their attitude toward the surroundings will be impacted if they are presented in harmony with the vibrant graphics on the computer. Words and images that reflect the new topic are displayed on the screen at this stage. Students will get the chance to listen and say things out loud. One should be mindful of the individualization of education principle when using a computer to present a topic. While some students have trouble understanding the word's sound picture, others have trouble understanding the word's graphic image. He or she will help the learner locate and get rid of the elements that will make it difficult for him or her to master the English language by using computer activities to aid overcome various challenges.

Age groups play a role in language learning. Psychologists claim that youngsters learn language more quickly and easily than adults. The primary causes of this include children's innate propensity for language acquisition, their powerful capacity for imitation, and the fact that they spend more time than adults. It should be highlighted that youngsters between the ages of 8 and 11 do not comprehend the significance of information; instead, they only mechanically recall it. Therefore, let's hold off on beginning to teach English to elementary school pupils with grammatical ideas.

Otherwise, the child can become frustrated with the first stage of learning a foreign language and lose interest.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that contemporary education is crucial. Modern information technology is increasingly useful in this procedure. Additionally, it is important to gain a thorough understanding of the planning and execution of contemporary didactic works based on pedagogical technologies that will fully satisfy students' interest and need in learning a foreign language while taking into account their age and psychological makeup when teaching English. The output offers a workable answer to the issue.

REFERENCES:

1. Bekmuratova U.B. Essay on "The use of innovative technologies in teaching English." Tashkent - 2012
2. N. Q. Xatamova, M.N.mirzayeva. "INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN ENGLISH LESSONS" (methodical manual), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages.
3. M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rixsittilayeva. "THE USE OF ASSISTANCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING". Tashkent: Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, 2005 O. Hoshimov, I. Yakubov.
4. Johnson, K. E. The Sociocultural Turn and Its Challenges for Second Language Teacher Education. // TESOL Quarterly., – London., 2006: – 235-pages.
5. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. – London., 2001: – 64-pages.
6. Indriyani. (2015). Method of teaching speaking to the seventh grade of SMP Muhammadiyah 2 Surakarta 2014/2015 academic year (Skripsi). Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta, Surakarta.